

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MODERN ORGANIZATIONAL FRAMEWORKS FOR BUSINESS PROCESS MANAGEMENT TO BE IMPLEMENTED IN THE POST-PANDEMIC REALITY

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Abstract

Purpose – The main research purpose was to understand the context in which innovation was adopted at the organizational level and what frameworks were encouraging transformation in the post-pandemic era. Because of new organization structures development, a new genre of organizational approach and the need of new professionals appeared to support these practices.

Methodology/approach – The approach for this research considered analyzing the two guides BABOK and BPM CBOK, identifying a common ground, modelling the main process, organizational frameworks and debating the differences using comparison analysis, having as a starting point core concepts common for both guides. Main methods used: comparison matrix, indicators as scope, common/different processes, performance indicators.

Findings – The findings captured the main similarities and differences among the modern organizational frameworks for business process management considering the criteria of analysis such as aim, structure, concepts, methodology for implementation, process components, etc.

Research limitations/implications – The research limitations provided by the analysis itself was aiming to analyze and compare strictly the two guides considering main common concepts and structure.

Practical implications – The current study could have practical implications and be used as a starting point for a in detail analysis regarding the way of framing business processes and introducing a change culture into the organization, also considered as the value of this paper.

Key words: Business process, organizational transformation, modern organizational frameworks

Introduction

In the past two years organizations faced many changes during an unprecedented pandemic, no matter the industry, the business processes had to be configured once again to the fast-changing environment. Analyzing and comparing two modern organizational business process frameworks, seeing how they are implemented nowadays, might bring solutions to prevent a high impact and more flexible solutions in case of calamity.

This paper can be considered theoretical research, exploring the comparison between two business organization process modelling frameworks: BABOK (Guide to the Business Analysis Body of Knowledge) and BPM CBOK (Guide to the Business Process Management Body of Knowledge), emphasizing the organization structure transformation needed in the post-pandemic reality.

Business process management represents a mix between management knowledge, a set of techniques and digital tools supporting managing by process. These frameworks developed by research entities as International Institute of Business Analysis (IIBA) and Association of Business Process Management Professionals (ABPMP) had been stressing on the need of organizations to become flexible, adaptable and able to redesign existing business processes. Hence the organizations should find ways to adapt and transform their structure at the same time, keeping the pace with the technological advancements and the post-pandemic reality.

Both guides have editions on the market since the 2000s, reviewed constantly from time to time. Because of the issues tackled in the literature review, and the stage at which the pandemic arrived, the frameworks discussed are fresh and up to date with the times lived. The organizational modelling matches the need of flexibility and changes required during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Both frameworks are including the introduction and knowledge about purpose and structure, main key concepts and definitions related to the subject for a better implementation understanding.

The BPM CBOK is covering main points related to business processes, from modelling, analysis, design, performance, transformation, and organization followed by enterprise process management and BPM technology. On the other hand, BABOK is presenting the aspects related to planning and monitoring, collaboration, lifecycle management, strategy analysis, design requirements, solution evaluation, competencies, and techniques.

There can be identified a middle ground for both guides, and that are the organizational approach or modelling and the idea of business transformation with the help of the business processes. In the case of any organization, processes evolve continuously if the business succeeds on the market. Then the process transformation represents the fundamental rethinking of that organizational structure, and more over the goal is innovation (the approaches, techniques and technologies enhancing the transformation). On the other hand, the business analysis core concept model guideline has been described under six core concepts (change, need, solution, stakeholder, value and context) regardless of the perspective, industry, way of application or level in the organization. Change represents the transformation of the business/process/product in response to a need. And then finding solution for that specific need. Hence this transformation also works to improve the performance of an organization. In this case in what degree is transformation considered innovative and becomes innovation for organizations having different structures?

Further on, some common concepts were identified and defined from the perspective of each guide and the first comparison was made. These concepts were business analysis, input and output of the process/project/organization, the stakeholders, the context and the idea of change and transformation related to the innovation side. Each one being a fundamental practice and part of the business processes and structure, as seen in Table 1.

Table 1 - Common concept comparison

Concept	BABOK	BPM CBOK
Business analysis	Defining needs and designing and describing solutions, within the boundaries of a project or throughout enterprise evolution.	Tool used by the analyst to understand the business environment and its changes, for discerning how processes might need to adapt.
Input	The needs met and the performance objectives set to be achieved.	Resources or data triggering the process components
Output	Stakeholder engagement, information management approach, methodologies and frameworks.	Services, products meeting or exceeding the stakeholders and the customers' expectations.
Stakeholder	A group or an individual acting for the organization's sake, through motivation, interest and change.	A group or an individual who could impact and be impacted by process / project / organizations' outcomes.
Context	The total components of an environment influencing and influenced by the change.	The total components of the business and process delivery achieving the organizations goals.
Change	Improving the performance of an enterprise using the addressed problems and opportunities.	The rethinking of a process and bringing improvement and performance to the organization.
Transformation	The data migration and molding the information into the processes.	A better way to do the work of the process through frameworks, tools, and equipment.

Methodology

This paper was using as literature review the BABOK and BPM CBOK guides, framing the analysis over following characteristics: scope, structure for implementing the guides, emphasizing the business processes, the process components and the need of business transformation in the post-pandemic era. Comparison tables were developed in order to show the common points and the differences between the frameworks.

Findings

The pressure for excellence and innovation, nowadays, had emphasized the role of process development for improving organizational knowledge and work through process-based approach. The pandemic environment forced organizations to reconfigure strategies, activities and governance.

Given the process management approach the organization could secure its operation processes on a constant basis, delivering the promised value to its customers and stakeholders. By designing end-to-end processes, aligning internal processes with strategies, defining proper governance and measurement systems, the organizations will be able to operate with lower costs, improved accuracy and high level of customer satisfaction.

Even if there is a substantial body of knowledge and an increasing interest on process-oriented approach, the challenges remain since applications without a solid theoretical foundation is extremely hazardous, especially when organizations adopt changes as a way of surviving this turbulent world. Thus, understanding main characteristics of processes and comparing different approaches of organizational structures may give a clear perspective of modern organizational frameworks.

Business process management frameworks

The scope of both guides is to provide sets of common accepted practices in their area of expertise. BABOK is offering a framework for defining and creating a profession as business analyst and BPM CBOK requires the fundamental knowledge for a BPM professional.

In the case of each one of the frameworks the structure is related to the knowledge areas covered, as seen in Table 2. Beyond the knowledge areas the structure of BABOK goes through Competencies, Techniques (similar with BPM Technologies) and Perspectives.

Table 2 - Knowledge areas

Knowledge areas	
BABOK	BPM CBOK
Business Analysis Planning and Monitoring	Enterprise Process Management (Enterprise perspective - EP)
Elicitation and Collaboration	Process Organization (EP)
Requirements Life Cycle Management	Process Modelling (Process Perspective – PP)
Strategy Analysis	Process Analysis (PP)
Requirements Analysis and Design Definition	Process Design (PP)
Solution Evaluation	Process Implementation (PP)
Competencies	Process Performance management (PP)
Techniques	Process Performance transformation (PP)
Perspectives	BPM Technologies (PP)

Were considered the following business process components by the BABOK framework: task, input, output, activity, and by BMP CBOK framework: subprocess, workflow, process roadmap. Both BABOK and BMP CBOK covered main understanding of the process components, as seen in Table 3.

Table 3 - Business process components

Process component	Characteristics
Task	A piece of work Performed formally or informally
Subprocess	Set of activities defining just a part of a process
Input	Resources used to start a process/subprocess/task
Output	Result produced by performing a task
Activity	An activity split into tasks
Workflow	Sequence of activities/processes including the aggregated information that has to be integrated with other business units
Process roadmap	Set of activities integrated across the process areas Following the inputs through the outputs into the result

To facilitate an organizational modelling for a modern organization, the main activities would be designing – definition of the future state of the organization/process/project; modelling – graphical representation of the organization structure and processes, shaping requirements and solution design specifications; execution and monitoring – iterating the process flow and finding alternatives for design improvement; optimizing – iteration of the previous phases.

Another important point considered was the proper governance. The business process is about creating rules and standards for the organization, identifying decision markers, the risk management and resource management plans, and the prioritization strategy.

Measuring performance is essential to know if the processes are efficient, being part of the value chain. The performance can be checked by the objective’s completion, by the governance strategy and by the overall stakeholders.

Organizational structure modelling

Any group coming together fulfilling the same scope using a similar set of skills and targeting the same market represents a unit which can be organized following a pattern. The models are inspired from the observed human behavior. This way, familiar patterns are used to improve the experience at work and in the same time imposing some rules and governance strategies.

The organizational structure or the organizational modelling are expressions used by both guides to express the visual representation of an organization. These representations are showing how roles and functions are spread in the organization and how the processes are assembled to support the execution.

A visual representation of the organizational structure usually is consisting of group managers, functional roles and formal relationships between the employees, interaction and dependencies of the unit with the stakeholders. Nowadays, a cross functional approach of managing business processes is used, hence specialized roles have to support the governance, the decision makers.

BABOK is classifying the types of organizational models by three main characteristics: functionally oriented, market oriented, and the matrix model. These three modern structures are usually depicting the organizational unit, roles and people and lines of reporting.

As BMP CBOK is more process oriented, the organizational models are shaped and labeled by the importance of leading roles and responsibilities for business process management. The leading role that may influence the organizational structure is the process owner, where a process owner represents a person or a group having this role for a complete end-to-end business process.

The responsibility for a business management process is assigned to the process owner, hence he is responsible for ensuring that the process meets the expected results. The organizational structure in this case can be split into two approaches: functionally aligned process ownership and non-functionally aligned ownership.

In the case of functionally aligned process ownership, process owners report to heads of functional units, either a single process owner is assigned for the whole unit, or the responsibility for process ownership is assigned to multiple process owners, basically being inside the unit structure. For the case of non-functionally aligned ownership approach, process owners report directly to the head of the organization, with the possibility to have a different branch managing the main business processes and providing business analysts, governors and leaders to projects from different units.

Business transformation

“In most cases, organizations have evolved in response to business needs.” (Moore, C., Saxena, R., Lee, D., & Powell, E, 2013, p.288) The structure is affected if the needs, the market and the objectives change. Nowadays, the technological advancements are happening very fast from many reasons, and organizations must have a continuous improvement and a multi-dimensional view, despite the human fear of change, or appearance of a new pandemic situation. This improvement is bringing a shift into the organizational culture transforming traditional organizations into learning organizations, always learning to improve processes and capabilities, to train human resources and adapt to the ongoing technology development and environment challenges.

The alignment of human resources – operations (processes) - technology is very important. Although in transformation all three previous mentioned actors are essential, most of the time the transformation starts from the business process and from the organizational structure. Being a departure from the companies past governance and way of thinking, often unconformable for the employees and managers.

Flexible organizational frameworks must nurture the collaborative working environment, compromising and yet producing an optimal solution, encouraging the acquisition and use of cross-cultural skills and the ability to iterate. Nowadays, business transformation, fosters emerging technologies and BPM methods.

According to Eurostat (2014), a total of 46 903 of enterprises in the EEA (European Economic Area), at that time 31 countries, had introduced new business practices for organizing procedures, new methods of organizing external relations, and new methods of organizing work responsibilities and decision making. Although, Germany had the highest number of enterprises for all three indicators and Malta and Iceland the lowest, the number of enterprises was unbalanced, because some big countries considering the territory and population, did not had a high number of enterprises embracing business transformation, for example Romania, with an average number of 350 enterprises for all three indicators.

However, these decisions related to transformation were not enough, they failed to prepare the markets, the industries, the economy for the shock and transformation waves brought by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Few years later, between 2018-2020, according to the National Institute of Statistics, Romania had a total of 702 enterprises using innovative business processes, where 81.9 percent developed their business process innovations in their own enterprise, 25.6 percent developed the innovations together with other enterprises, 12.3 percent implemented their innovations by adapting or modification of processes initially developed in other enterprises, and 5.3 percent had business process innovations developed by other enterprises.

Taking into considerations the behaviors and results for the pre-pandemic period, the impact shows a low number of organizations having flexibility and adaptation implementing frameworks as BABOK and BPM CBOK. Due to lack of studies from the post-pandemic period in-depth, a comparison it could not have been done, however this can be considered a possible direction of research in the next period.

Contributions

The authors made a synthesis and comparison of the research made over the two guides (BABOK and BPM CBOK), getting into detail about the organizational frameworks. Another important aspect was the data filtering and processing.

Conclusion

Considering the complexity of organizational environment, the paper had deciphered modern scientific literature in the attempt to provide understandings of the organizational processes concepts and related management systems. Aligning strategy to processes is made through the organizational structure, in the context of technological advancements and post-pandemic reality.

Both books used for the literature review are covering the need of structuring the visual representation of an organization in a modern approach, BPM CBOK emphasizing the roles of the business process responsible (process owner).

The biggest challenge in today's world to adapt in real time the activity to the technology, the market, and the environment threats. Business transformation brings many positive aspects, helping organizations to identify, prioritize and optimize their business processes to deliver value to the stakeholders.

Business transformation should involve seeking ideas from both inside and outside the organization, and be accepted and implemented by most organizations, considering the pandemic which just withered away, some time ago.

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